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MAN CONFRONTS NATURE - A CRITICAL STUDY OF ERNEST HEMINGWAY'S THE OLD MAN AND THE SEA

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Nature provides shelter for the human beings, and they are constantly surrounded by it and interact with it. If we lose nature's shelter, we lose our self. Natural things such as mountains, rivers, air, soil etc, plays a vital role in the life of human beings.

Ernest Hemingway was born on July 21, 1899. Hemingway played an important role in World War II. After the war was over, he retired to Cuba to fish. Hemingway's novel *The Old Man and the Sea* is a story where man confronts nature. Hemingway identifies himself with the old fisherman Santiago, who cleverly fights against natural forces. Most of Hemingway's novels revolve around a single character and his destiny. *The Old man and the sea* is also developed on the destiny of single man, the story of fisherman's journey, his long and lonely struggle with a fish and the sea, and his victory in defeat.

Life signifies nothingness, because death is immaterial from the point of nature. The fish eats the bait which was once alive creature and ultimately it is killed by the fisherman and this is

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transformed into different kind of substance. The sharks behave most naturally which kill the fish and humans catch the sharks. The life cycle is symbolized in nature. The old man reflects on his own destiny. The killer and the killed both have their own destiny.

In *The Old Man and the Sea*, Hemingway portrays human activities in which the individual could take a stance, even that of a “loser” and maintain his pride and manhood. Men are not different from animals in their deeds of life. It represents the basic attitudes of the human being. Here the weaker ones are destroyed by the stronger ones, “It is the fisherman’s job to kill a fish and it is the duty of a fish to get killed. The stronger kills the weaker and this fact have been accepted by Hemingway” (Deva 20).

In this novel Santiago’s behaviour with the marlin, whom he would kill shortly remains as noble as it can be. The old man says, “A man can be destroyed but not defeated” (89) and he consoles himself by saying that he thinks “perhaps it was a sin to kill a fish” (90).

Thus man confronts nature becomes obvious that the relationship with nature and his own nature leads to the final understanding of life. Santiago’s capacity to endure any hardship is revealed when even nature is unsupportive. Above all Santiago has that supreme power, the power of love. Santiago says, “ I will show him what a man can do and what a man endures” (53). It is here that Santiago becomes a great symbol and monument in all its glory of determination of mankind to face any challenge.

Works Cited:

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2. Prof. Som Deva. *A critical study of Ernest Hemingway and his Old Man and the Sea*. Bareilly: Literary Publication Bureau, 1971. Print.